

Fluorescent sensing of H_2PO_4^- by *in situ* prepared Cu^{2+} complex in aqueous medium via displacement approach

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Manuscript received 13 June 2017, accepted 15 June 2017

Abstract : The *in situ* prepared Cu^{2+} chelate of luminescent ligand, pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde-benzoic acid hydrazone (**1**) was investigated for fluorescent sensing of H_2PO_4^- in aqueous medium via restoration of the fluorescence intensity of the receptor through Cu^{2+} displacement approach. The sensing behavior of this ligand towards Cu^{2+} via fluorescence quenching has already been reported in our previous work. The present study depicts *in situ* prepared Cu^{2+} chelate as a turn-on fluorescent chemosensor of H_2PO_4^- detecting in the micro molar range. The Cu^{2+} chelate possesses excellent tolerance to other interfering anions Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , OAc^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} .

Keywords : Luminescent, hydrazone, fluorescent chemosensor, anion recognition, H_2PO_4^- .

Introduction

The development of anion selective sensors has received considerable attention in recent years as anions play a potential role in several environmental processes. Especially, chemosensors based on the anion induced luminescence changes are attractive due to the simplicity, selectivity and high sensitivity¹⁻³.

Among the significant anions, phosphate and its derivatives act as essential ingredients in biological systems and are responsible for different biological and environmental functions⁴⁻¹². Therefore, a number of phosphate recognition methods have been investigated¹³⁻¹⁸. At physiological pH phosphate exists as both H_2PO_4^- and HPO_4^{2-} ¹⁹ and the selective detection of dihydrogen phosphate (H_2PO_4^-) gets more attraction to the researchers in phosphate recognition. Due to the very high free energy of hydration ($\Delta G^0 = -465 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), it is difficult to design a chemosensor for H_2PO_4^- sensing in water²⁰. The receptors having the ability of detection of H_2PO_4^- in an aqueous medium at neutral pH is highly desirable and of special significance due to their potential applications in biological sciences^{21,22}. A number of chemosensors are developed that rely on hydrogen bonding via the amide²³,

urea and thiourea subunits²⁴. However, a serious disadvantage of such receptors is that they are not able to sense anions in aqueous solvents because the aqueous medium strongly competes for hydrogen bonding sites²⁵. To overcome this problem, sensory systems were developed in which an electrostatic affinity for transition metal ions facilitates a strong interaction²⁶. In the context of metal complexes as anion sensors, the paradigm has shifted toward the metal ion displacement approach where, a metal ion quenches the fluorescent intensity of the receptor and the treatment of such a metal complex with an anion displaces the metal ion from the coordination sphere of the original organic receptor, restoring the fluorescence intensity of the receptor²⁷⁻²⁹. However, a lot of works have already been reported and most of the receptors are developed using tedious synthetic protocols and sometimes shows poor compatibility in water³⁰⁻³⁶.

Earlier the selective response of the receptor **1** (pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde-benzoic acid hydrazone) towards Cu^{2+} was investigated and reported³⁷. In continuation to the previous work herein we have explored the sensing behavior of the *in situ* prepared Cu^{2+} chelate, **1**- Cu^{2+} , towards H_2PO_4^- by turn-on mechanism via Cu^{2+} displacement approach.

Table 1. Some reported receptors used for H_2PO_4^- sensing via metal displacement approach

Sl. No.	Structure	Metal displaced	Quantum yield of receptor	Limit of detection of receptor-metal chelate	Reference
1.		Zn^{2+}	–	–	30
2.		Zn^{2+}	–	–	31
3.		Cu^{2+}	–	1.41 μM	32
4.		Zn^{2+}	2.0×10^{-3}	–	33

Table-1 (contd.)

5.		Fe^{3+}	0.89	$1.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mol/L}$	34
6.		Cu^{2+}	–	–	35
7.		Fe^{3+}	–	$1.69 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol/L}$	36
8.		Cu^{2+}	0.0167	$2.53 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$	37 and the present work

Experimental

Reagents :

All starting materials and solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and Merck chemical company and used without further purification unless otherwise stated.

Physical measurements :

Spectroscopic studies were carried out with a Hitachi-F7000 Luminescence Spectrometer at ambient temperature in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v) at fixed concentration of **1** ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$). Titration experiments were carried out in 10-mm quartz cuvettes at 25 °C. Copper(II) salt and anions as tetrabutylammonium salts (1 μM ; except for NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-}) in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v) were added to the host solution and used for the titra-

tion experiment. **1**- Cu^{2+} solution for H_2PO_4^- detection was prepared by addition of 1.0 equiv. of Cu^{2+} to compound **1** solution in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v). Mass spectra were recorded using Xevo G2-SQT.

Synthesis and characterization of receptors :

The receptor (**1**) was synthesized following the reported method³⁷. The characterization data and the single crystal X-ray structure of the receptor **1** were already reported in our previous work³⁷.

Results and discussion

Spectral studies :

The binding stoichiometry of the receptor **1** with Cu^{2+} ion was found to be 1 : 1 as reported in our

previous work³⁷. The positive ion mass spectrum of **1** upon addition of Cu^{2+} indicated that a peak at $m/z = 401.10$ which was assignable to $[\mathbf{1} + \text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{Br}^- + \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (Calcd. 401.65). Thus, the 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ chelate was also supported by the ESI-mass spectrometry analysis.

The sensing of **1** towards Cu^{2+} was reported in our earlier study³⁷. The $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ chelate exhibits strong absorption band in the visible region ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 435 \text{ nm}$) in aqueous medium. The emission peak of **1** ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 405 \text{ nm}$), undergoes quenching upon complexation with Cu^{2+} ³⁷. In the present work, the *in situ* prepared Cu^{2+} chelate was investigated as a turn-on fluorescent chemosensor for H_2PO_4^- ions in aqueous medium. The successive addition of H_2PO_4^- (0–100 μM) to the *in situ* prepared solution of $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ (10 μM) resulted in a step-wise enhancement of emission intensity at 405 nm and gradually restored to the original emission state of **1** (Fig. 1). The proposed binding mode of receptor **1** involving Cu^{2+} and H_2PO_4^- ions is illustrated in Scheme 1. Fluorescence-ON receptor **1** selectively binds to Cu^{2+} to form a Fluorescence-OFF $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ chelate. This is accompanied by the loss of a proton as revealed from mass spectroscopic studies. The $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ chelate selectively interacts with H_2PO_4^- thereby resulted in the restoration of the Fluorescence-ON emission spectra of receptor **1**.

The detection limit of the $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ chelate as a fluorescent sensor for the analysis of H_2PO_4^- was determined from a plot of emission intensity as a function of concentration of the added anion. Based on the emission titration curve it was found that the fluores-

Fig. 1. Emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 290 \text{ nm}$) of $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ (10 μM) upon successive addition of H_2PO_4^- (0–100 μM) in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v) at 298 K.

cence enhancement factor $(I - I_0)/I_0$ was proportional to the concentration of H_2PO_4^- ions (Fig. 2). The linear range of fluorescence response of $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ for H_2PO_4^- ions was 0–10 μM ($R^2 = 0.9818$) and detection limit for H_2PO_4^- ions was calculated as $2.53 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$ following the reported method^{38–40}.

The response of $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ (10 μM) with selected anions (H_2PO_4^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , AcO^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}) was examined through spectrofluorimetric study in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v) at 298 K. The intensity of $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ solution containing other competitive anions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , OAc^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}) and H_2PO_4^- ions is shown in Fig. 3, indicating negligible interference of other anions for selective sensing of H_2PO_4^- via Cu^{2+} displacement approach.

A plot of I/I_0 (where, I and I_0 represent the fluo-

Scheme 1. Proposed mechanism of fluorescence sensing of H_2PO_4^- by $\mathbf{1}\text{-Cu}^{2+}$.

Fig. 2. (a) Plot of the fluorescence enhancement factor $(I - I_0)/I_0$ at 405 nm versus the concentration of H_2PO_4^- ions added. (b) Representation of linear range.

Fig. 3. (a) Changes in the fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 290 \text{ nm}$) of 1-Cu^{2+} ($10 \mu\text{M}$) upon addition of tetrabutylammonium salts of anions ($100 \mu\text{M}$) in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v). (b) Changes in the emission intensity of 1-Cu^{2+} ($10 \mu\text{M}$) on addition of H_2PO_4^- ($100 \mu\text{M}$) over selected anions ($100 \mu\text{M}$) in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v) at 405 nm at 298 K. The blue bars represent the emission intensity of 1-Cu^{2+} in the presence of selected anions; the red bars represent the emission intensity of the above solution on addition of H_2PO_4^- .

Fig. 4. Emission intensity ratios (I/I_0) for 1-Cu^{2+} ($10 \mu\text{M}$) at 405 nm in the presence of selected anions in aqueous medium ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 1 : 4, v/v) at 298 K.

rescence intensity of various metal ions and that of free metal respectively) at 405 nm (Fig. 4), shows a ratio ≈ 1 for most of the metal ions with the notable enhancement in emission intensity (> 8 -fold) for H_2PO_4^- ions.

Conclusion

The *in situ* prepared 1-Cu^{2+} chelate was investigated as a fluorescent sensor for H_2PO_4^- by the Cu^{2+} displacement approach in aqueous medium. No significant interference was observed in presence of selected anions. The sensor 1-Cu^{2+} was highly sensitive and selective for H_2PO_4^- with detection limit in the micro molar range.

Acknowledgement

Financial supports received from DST-PURSE and DST-FIST, New Delhi, India, are gratefully acknowledged for financial support and instrumental facilities. We are also grateful to the University of Kalyani for providing infrastructural facilities.

References

1. E. L. Que, D. W. Domaille and C. J. Chang, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 1517.
2. R. W. Sinkeldam, N. J. Greco and Y. Tor, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 2579.
3. R. M. Duke, E. B. Veale, F. M. Pfeffer, P. E. Kruger and T. Gunnlaugsson, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 3936.
4. H.-W. Rhee, S. J. Choi, S. H. Yoo, Y. O. Jang, H. H. Park, R. M. Pinto, J. C. Cameselle, F. J. Sandoval, S. Roje, K. Han, D. S. Chung, J. Suh and J.-I. Hong, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 10107.
5. J. M. Berg, J. L. Tymoczko and L. Stryer, "Biochemistry", 5th ed., Freeman, New York, 2002.
6. W. N. Lipscomb and N. Strater, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 2375.
7. K. Ghosh, D. Kar and P. R. Chowdhury, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 5098.
8. "Phosphorus in the Global Environment : Transfers, Cycles, and Management", ed. H. Tiessen, Wiley, New York, 1995.
9. C. F. Mason, "Biology of Freshwater Pollution", Longman, New York, 1991.
10. R. Dhingra, L. M. Sullivan, C. S. Fox, T. J. Wang, R. B. D. Agostino, J. M. Gaziano and R. S. Vasani, *Arch. Intern. Med.*, 2007, **167**, 879.
11. F. Albaaj and A. Hutchison, *Drugs*, 2003, **63**, 577.
12. E. W. Young, J. M. Albert, S. Satayathum, D. A. Goodkin, R. L. Pisoni, T. Akiba, T. Akizawa, K. Kurokawa, J. Bommer, L. Piera and F. K. Port, *Kidney Int.*, 2005, **67**, 1179.
13. J. Feng, Y. Chen, J. Pu, X. Yang, C. Zhang, S. Zhu, Y. Zhao, Y. Yuan, H. Yuan and F. Liao, *Anal. Biochem.*, 2011, **409**, 144.
14. W.-L. Cheng, J.-W. Sue, W.-C. Chen, J.-L. Chang and J.-M. Zen, *Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **82**, 1157.
15. I. Abulkalam, A. P. Suresh and K. Pitchumani, *Sens. Actuators B : Chem.*, 2011, **155**, 909.
16. Z. Xu, N. J. Singh, J. Lim, J. Pan, H. N. Kim, S. Park, K. S. Kim and J. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 15528.
17. V. V. Kumar and S. P. Anthony, *New J. Chem.*, 2015, **39**, 1308.
18. D. Zhang, J. R. Cochrane, A. Martinez and G. Gao, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 29735.
19. R. S. Dickins and D. Parker, "Macrocyclic Chemistry : Current Trends and Future Perspectives", ed. K. Gloe, Springer, 2005.
20. J. I. Bruce, R. S. Dickins, L. J. Govenlock, T. Gunnlaugsson, S. Lopinski, M. P. Lowe, D. Parker, R. D. Peacock, J. J. B. Perry, S. Aime and M. Botta, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 9674.
21. V. Guerschais and J.-L. Fillaut, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2011, **255**, 2448.
22. R. M. Duke and T. Gunnlaugsson, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 1503.
23. E. J. O'Neil and B. D. Smith, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 3068.
24. G. Saikia and P. K. Iyer, *Macromolecules*, 2011, **44**, 3753.
25. R. M. Duke and T. Gunnlaugsson, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 5402.
26. M. Bhuyan, E. Katayev, S. Stadlbauer, H. Nonaka, A. Ojida, I. Hamachi and B. Konig, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, 2807.
27. D.-L. Ma, V. P.-Y. Ma, D. S.-H. Chan, K.-H. Leung, H.-Z. He and C.-H. Leung, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **256**, 3087.
28. J. F. Callan, A. P. de Silva and D. C. Magri, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 8551.
29. P. Saluja, N. Kaur, N. Singh and D. O. Jang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2012, **53**, 3292.
30. M. Zhang, W. Lu, J. Zhou, G. Du, L. Jiang, J. Ling and Z. Shen, *Tetrahedron*, 2014, **70**, 1011.
31. S. Goswami, S. Maity, A. C. Maity, A. K. Das, K. Khanra, T. K. Mandal and N. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2014, **55**, 5993.
32. H. Goh, Y. G. Ko, T. K. Nam, A. Singh, N. Singh and D. O. Jang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2016, **57**, 4435.
33. A. Hens, P. Mondal and K. K. Rajak, *Polyhedron*, 2015, **85**, 255.
34. L. Jun, L. Qi, Z. YouMing and W. TaiBao, *Sci. China Chem.*, 2014, **57**, 1257.
35. Z. Chen, L. Wang, G. Zou, X. Cao, Y. Wu and P. Hu, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A : Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2013, **114**, 323.
36. T. Wei, G. Wu, B. Shi, Q. Lin, H. Yao and Y. Zhang, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 2014, **32**, 1238.
37. S. Mukherjee, P. Mal and H. Stoeckli-Evans, *J. Luminescence*, 2014, **155**, 185.
38. N. Zhang, F. Qu, H. Q. Luo and N. B. Li, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2013, **791**, 46.
39. S. Mukherjee, P. Mal and H. Stoeckli-Evans, *J. Luminescence*, 2016, **172**, 124.
40. Y.-J. Chang, P.-J. Hung, C.-F. Wan and A.-T. Wu, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2014, **39**, 122 and references therein.